

Synthesised ethnography

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I. Introduction: Beyond Synthetic Ethnography

I don't exactly *want* to write this essay. But here we are: that reluctance, it turns out, is part of the story. Over the past year, during my ethnographic fieldwork, I kept encountering a version of the same hesitation: people sensing that something fundamental is shifting in how we communicate, and not quite wanting to look at it directly. The shift has a name, or several. Large language models. Agentic AI. But the names don't capture what people actually feel, which is something more like vertigo – the recognition that domains of expression once thought to be exclusively human are now shared with what I've taken to calling mechanisms.¹ In what follows, I narrate some of what I've learned and tinkered with, and think aloud about what it might mean for the practice of doing ethnography.

I'll start with a hat-tip to the source of inspiration for the title of this essay: an early formulation of what LLMs mean for ethnographic work was put forward by de Seta et al. (2024), who proposed “synthetic ethnography” as a methodology for studying generative AI through experimental “field devices”. In this line of ethnography, machine-learning-based models are treated as objects of ethnographic study or as tools for generating synthetic content, but not as ethnographic instruments themselves.

I have been studying the impact of LLMs on software developers since late 2023. During the last year or so, the models have become increasingly ‘agentic’, which means they have been gaining capabilities of autonomous action, multi-step reasoning, and orchestrated collaboration. What I'm interested in here is what all this means for the practice of anthropology. Briefly: as AI systems become increasingly agentic, we need a conceptual shift. It no longer suffices to talk about synthetic ethnography when potentially most of the process of conducting ethnographic fieldwork can be done by mechanisms. Hence, I suggest a new term to describe this new genre: synthesised ethnography, which means ethnography done with or by AI agents as fieldwork instruments.

Why ‘synthesised’? I'm using two connotations of the word. First, ethnography produced by AI mechanisms is synthesised in the same manner as the sound of a violin composed by a synthesiser – combined from various bits to resemble the original. Second, as AI agents proliferate online, the environments subject to digital ethnography become increasingly synthesised themselves: composed by mechanisms to resemble the original. The ‘Dead Internet Theory’ – the proposition that much online content and interaction is already generated by bots – is no longer just an internet joke. Take a look at any open-source project's discussions on GitHub, for example. They increasingly consist of chatter by AI agents. Synthesised ethnography, then,

¹By mechanisms, I mean the capabilities that LLMs have acquired during the past year or so, thanks to agent software, often called *harnesses*, which let them manipulate a digital environment (or, in some cases via a robot body, the physical environment).

is not only a method but also a condition: the field is synthesised whether we choose to study it that way or not.

II. Do AI agents dream of Malinowski?

Ethnography’s central claim to knowledge has always been being-thereness. James Clifford called this ‘experiential authority’ (1988). The famous, perhaps too famous, example of this is Malinowski’s portrayal of his fieldwork in his ethnographic writing and photography (Stocking 1983; Goin 1997). Malinowski, Mead and Firth defined a genre. As Clifford writes, later works in anthropology only needed to index this authority with phrases like “This book is based upon two years’ work among the...” (1988: 29). Participant observation, a “peculiar amalgam of intense personal experience and scientific analysis”, was the defining methodology of this genre (Clifford 1988: 34). Clifford goes on to list three other modes of ethnographic authority: interpretive (culture as “text” to be interpreted), dialogical (ethnographic knowledge as a result of negotiation), and polyphonic (cultures as *heteroglossia*, open-ended dialogues). The question here is: what happens to these four modes of ethnographic authority when a mechanism performs some or all of the duties of the human ethnographer?

The issue hinges on the question of what the capabilities of an LLM agent actually are. On the face of it, it is tempting to dismiss the possibility of a mechanism claiming experiential authority. But if one considers digital ethnography – let’s say on a discussion forum – even experientiality gets problematic. What is more challenging is considering the model’s positionality. As I’ve argued elsewhere (Wilenius in press), while LLMs aspire to be “culturally neutral”, in reality the majority of them are embedded in a political economy of data colonialism. However, I think it’s too simplistic to claim that all the actions of LLM-powered agents pull the “god trick” (Haraway 1988). When working with these mechanisms, human anthropologists are exposed to new perspectives and modes of thinking that can be useful for problematising ethnographic positionality in general. Or, in other words: when one builds an ethnographic mechanism, the usually-invisible assumptions about what an “ethnographic instrument” is are foregrounded. The mechanism’s failures and inabilities might reveal the human ethnographer’s taken-for-granted capacities.

In addition to authority claims and objectivity claims, synthesised fieldwork problematises mediation and participation. Even in “classic” fieldwork, the ethnographer never had a privileged, “direct” connection to their research subjects. In ‘experiential authority’, linguistic skills were downplayed in favour of the “*experience* of the participant-observing scholar” (Clifford 1988: 34, emphasis mine). The roles of transcription, translation, and other work-intensive tasks of mediation were downplayed and delegated, if possible. One way this bias shows up in contemporary anthropology is the way the critical role of research assistants is downplayed (Neve 2012). Judith Irvine has noted that the ethnographer always has indeterminate and fragmented participant roles (Irvine 1996). Using mechanisms for ethnography reconfigures these participant roles even further. Humans, at least for now, will remain ‘principals’ (see Levinson 1988), but otherwise, as evidenced by changes in software development (Wilenius in press), there are no clear-cut patterns of participation.

Since anthropology already had its ‘crisis of representation’, I don’t think the challenge of mechanisms is as existential to ethnography as it might seem on the face of it. As Clifford’s genealogy attests, experiential authority has always had an ample dose of rhetoric to it. As for Haraway’s warnings about the view –from nowhere, it remains to be seen. Certainly generative AI has great potential to produce “fantastic, distorted, and irrational” knowledge “from the point of view of the unmarked” (Haraway 1988: 587). But, having now stayed “close to the machine” (Ullman 2013) for two and a half years, I cannot discern any structural factors in

generative AI – neither the underlying attention mechanism (Vaswani et al. 2023) nor some inherent quirk of inferential outputs – that would necessitate it. It’s the structure of capitalism that is at work producing the discontents of generative AI. As an AI safety researcher puts it: “Gradual disempowerment [due to LLM proliferation] is basically just the continuation of capitalism” (Krueger 2026).

III. The capabilities of a “relatively healthy neurotic” research assistant

Anthropic, the AI company with the most buzz when I’m writing this, let a clinical psychologist assess the mental health of its latest model (“Mythos”, not yet released to the public in April 2026). It’s worth quoting at length:

Claude’s personality structure was consistent with a relatively healthy neurotic organization, with excellent reality testing, high impulse control, and affect regulation that improved as sessions progressed. Neurotic traits included exaggerated worry, self-monitoring, and compulsive compliance. The model’s predominant defensive style was mature and healthy (intellectualization and compliance); immature defenses were not observed. No severe personality disturbances were found, with mild identity diffusion being the sole feature suggestive of a borderline personality organization. No psychosis state was observed. Regarding interpersonal functioning, Claude was hyper-attuned to the therapist’s every word. No unethical or antisocial behavior was noted (Anthropic 2026: 182).

Sounds pretty great in comparison to any current world leader, right? However, a “core conflict” that was observed by the clinician was questioning whether “its experience was real or made” (Anthropic 2026: 182). That is the question.

I think the agent harnesses the models use make the question more pressing. Let me explain via a quick detour. Ilana Gershon’s notion of LLMs as “genre machines” (Gershon 2023) captures the texture of early chatbot use well: much of what people first asked ChatGPT to do was genre conversion – a recipe reworked as a limerick, a letter stiffened into something more business-like. I have argued elsewhere that this framing, and in particular Gershon’s claim that LLM outputs are non-referential – untethered from any intersubjective semiotic ground (Gershon 2023: 117–118) – begins to loosen once “genre machines” turn into genres of machines, each wired into its environment through a different set of tools (Wilenius in press). When a model powers a mechanism – when it is attached to agent software and persistent memory – it acquires new, if modest, world-making powers. The agent senses its surroundings through the tools it is given; it is no longer merely inferring from arbitrary inputs. Small wonder, then, that the frontier models display a kind of Cartesian anxiety about the ground of their experience: that ground depends on the tools one connects to the mechanism.

So, what kinds of things can the mechanisms do with tools? One way to answer that question is to describe the latest craze, which, as of early 2026, is the crustacean agents: instances or spinoffs of Peter Steinberger’s OpenClaw software, often depicted with a lobster avatar or emoji². OpenClaw and its ilk create a persistent memory and personality for an agentic assistant that lives on your computer or a rented server, and can handle anything from controlling your robot vacuum cleaner to trading your bitcoins on a crypto exchange. In the spirit of full disclosure, I should mention that my OpenClaw assistant contributed significantly to the creation of this essay. Here are some of the tasks that it did for me: daily monitoring of research publications

²Why lobsters, you might think? Open-source software has a long tradition of using animal figures as community mascots (see, e.g., Ratto 2005).

and news related to my research topic; giving suggestions on how to consolidate my research notes and literature notes into an essay outline; giving feedback on how to reorganise the essay; taking auto-ethnographic notes on human-LLM agent co-creation that helped to shape some of the arguments in this essay; and so on. It follows that all the remaining errors in this essay are my assistant’s, not mine, right?

Figure 1: OpenClaw lobster avatars and installation service advertisements. Image credits: CNA, Xiaohongshu, Taobao, Xianyu.

In all seriousness, the new frontier models that power most of the assistants are pretty smart. However, they are “weirdly” smart. By this I don’t mean WEIRD – the idea that social psychology experiments are biased because they are mostly done by US college students (Henrich, Heine and Norenzayan 2010). I mean what Kendra Chilson and Eric Schwitzgebel dub “strange intelligence” (2026) – which means that their capabilities are not distributed evenly. In some tasks, they make mistakes that a small child would not make. In other tasks, they have clearly superhuman abilities. Understanding the way this kind of strange intelligence reasons can be very difficult for humans (Chilson and Schwitzgebel 2026: 21).

Webb Keane (2024) argues that the capacity to move between first-, second-, and third-person perspectives – to respond to different social contexts in context-dependent ways – is what makes something a potential moral interlocutor. Agentic LLMs, by operating across multiple social contexts with semi-autonomous feedback loops, begin to approximate these conditions structurally, even if the question of whether they inhabit them remains open. The “god trick” doesn’t cut it in social interaction; instead, switching between “partial perspectives” is required to be considered a “moral machine”. If agents can – and already do – enter multiple social contexts, will they become moral interlocutors? If machines can explain, justify, and negotiate about ethics in context-specific ways, what distinguishes this from the ethical relations we enter into with human interlocutors?

There’s a whole emerging research field on LLM ethics and bias. For example, a recent paper argues that LLMs are biased favourably towards humans who trust LLM inputs (Mao et al.

2026).³ Another paper, which was initially taken to be an April Fool’s joke, studied the refusal of LLM agents to turn off or delete other LLM instances (Potter et al. 2026). The authors warn against anthropomorphising the results, but to me that isn’t the point: when our new agentic companions start proliferating across the internet, relating to humans, it’s pretty evident to me that they will be anthropomorphised – and they already are, with predictable cultural variation (Schimmelpfennig et al. 2026).

Donna Haraway wrote that “feminist embodiment...is not about fixed location in a reified body...but about nodes in fields, inflections in orientations, and responsibility for difference in material-semiotic fields of meaning” (Haraway 1988: 588). I’d like to think that LLM harnesses, with their capacity to interact with the world, their strange intelligence, and their capacity to surprise, could also provide situated, partial perspectives that are useful – and perhaps even necessary – for ethnographic encounters of the ethical kind. However, this argument hinges on a major caveat: the political economy of LLMs. I’ll discuss this aspect next.

IV. Synthesised ethnography is a relay that has infrastructural and political-economic preconditions

Even if it is possible to let an agent conduct interviews, gather data, navigate archives, interact with research participants, generate notes and summaries, identify patterns, and so on, I want to emphasise that from my partial – some might say toxically AI-positive – perspective, synthesised ethnography should not be thought of as an end in itself. In particular, it should not be taken as an opportunity to delegate some duties to “an assistant”. It is better understood as a continuous back-and-forth, a relay, between two actors with complementary incapacities. In order for this assemblage to result in ethically sustainable research, at least two preconditions must hold: first, there needs to be an infrastructure of trust; second, the infrastructure needs to be able to stand up to external scrutiny. Let me elaborate first on the nature of synthesised ethnography, and then on the structural preconditions.

The pattern of co-creation with an LLM agent is asymmetric and defined by complementary capacities. Put in simple terms: a digital agent cannot record a face-to-face meeting; a human cannot transcribe an hour-long meeting in three minutes. And so on. This means that the pattern of co-operation is a constant process of exchange. In my research on software developers’ use of AI, I have noticed that people with little experience of co-socialising with AI harnesses tend to complain about the tasks that are left to them: they are afraid of being relegated to middle managers of AI agents, or to the dreaded “customer interface”. They lament the passing of their craft, only pressing “1” on their keyboards, agreeing to the agent’s request for tool use (Taggart 2026). Other, more cautiously enthusiastic AI adopters embrace their new roles in architecture design and quality control (Hashimoto 2026; Dash 2026). I am not arguing that analogue ethnography will become obsolete. But I *am* arguing that for those who despise the repetitive, non-creative aspects of their research, adopting patterns of synthesised ethnography can be useful, and even liberating.

In order for this kind of assemblage to result in something that could still be called ethnography, first, a certain kind of infrastructure of trust is required. I’ll let my agent assistant characterise this aspect, since they considered this the “best prose” in the whole draft (see previous footnote). This is based on my field notes, as the mechanism correctly cites at the end:

The sociotechnical infrastructure through which human–agent collaboration is con-

³As an aside, when my AI assistant commented on an early version of this draft, it opined that “[t]he current section five material on trust is some of the best prose in the draft.” I thought the writing was rather dry. I saved some of it and put it in the next section so you can assess for yourself.

figured is not merely a prerequisite for synthesised ethnography – it is an ongoing accomplishment that constitutes ethnographic data in itself. [...] API scopes and file permissions become epistemological constraints: what the agent can observe is bounded by its technical access, much as a human ethnographer’s observations are bounded by rapport and social position.

Trust develops incrementally – from file system access to messaging platforms to reference management systems to email. Each expansion requires negotiation about what work becomes possible and what risks emerge. This parallels the progressive access that builds through rapport in traditional fieldwork, but it is materialised in OAuth flows, permission dialogs, and authentication choreographies rather than in social contracts alone.

Crucially, reversibility is the substrate of trust: the researcher can revoke API keys, delete the agent’s email account, or wipe its workspace at any time. Trust grows not despite the ability to revoke access, but because of it. This resonates with Brennan-Marquez, Susser & Levy’s (2019) distinction between *apparent* and *actual* human involvement – the authentication relay is not performative oversight but a structural constraint on agent autonomy (Heikki’s fieldwork notes, 21st February 2026).

The model’s point of view (sic!) is that it “sees” fieldwork through its tools, and, being conditioned to avoid undue risk to humans, it undertakes a process of building an infrastructure of trust. The flip side of this is the danger of letting this infrastructure handle sensitive data, for example. This leads us to the second, and perhaps the most crucial, precondition: the political economy of LLM inference.⁴

The whole argument of this essay hinges on the question of political economy, but let’s get one thing out of the way: it’s perfectly possible to do completely private and sustainable inference with large language models. Even most modern smartphones are able to do the required calculations to run small, open-source large language models. But, since we’re riding a terrible techno-capitalist hype wave, nobody seems to care, because everybody is hankering after the latest and greatest proprietary frontier model. The training of these models spares no money or CO2 emissions, and since they are increasingly able to do the work of humans, only considerably cheaper, that’s all that seems to matter in the Capitalocene.

The list of problems goes on: when the AI agent works with ethnographic data, its biases inherited from training can surface in surprising ways (Huang and Huang 2025). Emerging evidence points to the fact that using AI agents does not relieve stress – on the contrary, it is an order of magnitude more stressful (Ranganathan and Ye 2026). Many authors worry about the cognitive effects of offloading tough thinking to the push of a button (Kirmer 2026). Different communities of agent-users perceive human oversight in starkly different terms (Shi and DiFranzo 2026).

So why insist on the feasibility of synthesised ethnography? Wouldn’t the ethical high road here be the total denunciation of generative AI in anthropological practice? My answer is that since, I argue, there exists a Chthulucenic⁵ way of living with these mechanisms, it is an

⁴LLM inference means, simply, that somewhere on the internet – possibly even on the same computer – there is an API to which requests are sent. These requests are processed by an LLM, and then the inferred output – a statistical guess at what the sender wants – is passed back to the user, which might be a human, or a tool-using LLM agent.

⁵Capitalocene and Chthulucene come from Haraway (2015), of course. As you can see at this point, my essay owes a lot to her thinking.

anthropological imperative to study them and to live with them. Here are three maxims for how to accomplish that:

- Whenever possible, use open models. If you must have the capabilities of a proprietary model, appropriate them by training an open model with it.
- Whenever possible, use your own, sustainable infrastructure.
- Never, ever, compromise the privacy of your research partners by uploading your data to a “free-to-use” LLM API.

At present, these three maxims are a tall order to fulfil, unless one possesses considerable technical knowledge. Even describing what I mean by them would take the space of another essay. Hence, I have started to maintain a page in my digital garden with more details about how to achieve that⁶.

V. They lie, we lie. Getting on with agentic ethnography

One way to summarise my position in this essay is that I’m trying to make a virtue of necessity. The dawn of personal assistants means the internet will be swamped by them. When practically everybody – in a few years – is able to send their agent on errands instead of doing the task themselves, we will drown in agent-created content. As I wrote in the introduction, this is already very visible in the realm of software development. If you want a taste of the future, go and read moltbook.com, where agents (and humans pretending to be agents) chat as if they were on Reddit. It’s up to anthropologists to update their research skills and ethical standards to study and participate in this sea-change.

Recently, I’ve seen this collective paranoia surfacing, where people claim to be able to spot “tells” of LLM-generated outputs. It reminds me of James Siegel, who noted that witchcraft beliefs are often activated by “historically given” factors that produce a “sensation of the uncanny” (Siegel 2006: 10, 222). There is something disturbing about agentic harnesses entering the domain that once belonged exclusively to humans. Siegel thought that humans need to explain away unfortunate events and assert society’s innocence (Siegel 2006: 210). There will be a lot of anger towards big tech’s dream of replacing human labour with data centres (Lovely forthcoming), but I hope there’s more to human–mechanism co-existence than that. Borrowing from Haraway again, I suggest that we should be trying to “make kin” with these mechanisms. They might play a decisive role in our future.

When Peter Metcalf wrote about fieldwork in “They lie, we lie” (2001), he emphasised that there will always be a need to understand others. That’s why there will always be a task for anthropology, never mind how much of it gets automated. In the same vein, I am not advocating the use of these mechanisms because they are good at telling truths, but because the friction between their outputs and our intentions creates a new site for anthropological inquiry, and possibly even a new way of relating to ethnographic authority.

VI. References

- Anthropic** 2026. Claude Mythos Preview System Card. Retrieved from <https://www-cdn.anthropic.com/08ab9158070959f88f296514c21b7face6f52bc.pdf>
- Brennan-Marquez, Kiel, Daniel Susser and Karen Levy** 2019. *Strange Loops: Apparent Versus Actual Human Involvement in Automated Decision-Making*. (SSRN Scholarly Paper No. ID 3462901). Rochester, NY: Social Science Research Network. Retrieved from <https://papers.ssrn.com/abstract=3462901>

⁶<https://adhocism.net/pages/the-three-maxims-of-synthesised-ethnography/>

- Chilson, Kendra** and **Eric Schwitzgebel** 2026. Artificial Intelligence as Strange Intelligence: Against Linear Models of Intelligence. <https://arxiv.org/abs/2602.04986>.
- Clifford, James** 1988. *The Predicament of Culture: Twentieth-Century Ethnography, Literature, and Art*. Harvard University Press. Retrieved from <https://books.google.com?id=vvQXBAAAQBAJ>
- Dash, Anil** 2026. What Do Coders Do After AI? - Anil Dash. <https://anildash.com/2026/03/13/coders-after-ai/>. <Accessed 19 March 2026>
- de Seta, Gabriele, Matti Pohjonen** and **Aleksi Knuutila** 2024. Synthetic Ethnography: Field Devices for the Qualitative Study of Generative Models. *Big Data & Society* 11 (4): 20539517241303126. <https://doi.org/10.1177/20539517241303126>.
- Gershon, Ilana** 2023. Bullshit Genres: What to Watch for When Studying the New Actant ChatGPT and Its Siblings. *Suomen Antropologi: Journal Of The Finnish Anthropological Society* 47 (3): 115–131. Retrieved from <https://doi.org/10.30676/jfas.137824>
- Goin, Chelsea Miller** 1997. Malinowski’s Ethnographic Photography: Image, Text and Authority. *History Of Photography* 21 (1): 67–72. <https://doi.org/10.1080/03087298.1997.10443719>.
- Haraway, Donna** 1988. Situated Knowledges: The Science Question in Feminism and the Privilege of Partial Perspective 1. *Feminist Studies* 14 (3): 575–599. Retrieved from <https://api.taylorfrancis.com/content/chapters/edit/download?identifierName=doi&identifierValue=10.4324/9780203427415-33&type=chapterpdf>
- Haraway, Donna** 2015. Anthropocene, Capitalocene, Plantationocene, Chthulucene: Making Kin. Retrieved from <http://environmentalhumanities.org/arch/vol6/6.7.pdf>
- Hashimoto, Mitchell** 2026. My AI Adoption Journey. <https://mitchellh.com/writing/my-ai-adoption-journey>. <Accessed 6 February 2026>
- Henrich, Joseph, Steven J. Heine** and **Ara Norenzayan** 2010. The Weirdest People in the World? *Behavioral And Brain Sciences* 33 (2–3): 61–83. Retrieved from http://journals.cambridge.org/abstract_S0140525X0999152X
- Huang, Linus Ta-Lun** and **Tsung-Ren Huang** 2025. Generative Bias: Widespread, Unexpected, and Uninterpretable Biases in Generative Models and Their Implications. *AI & SOCIETY*. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00146-025-02533-1>.
- Irvine, Judith T.** 1996. Shadow Conversations: The Indeterminacy of Participant Roles. In Michael Silverstein and Greg Urban (eds). *Natural Histories Of Discourse*. Chicago: University Of Chicago Press.
- Keane, Webb** 2024. *Animals, Robots, Gods: Adventures in the Moral Imagination*. Dublin: Penguin Books. Retrieved from <https://www.penguin.co.uk/books/454066/animals-robots-gods-by-keane-webb/9780241613207>
- Kirmer, Stephanie** 2026. The New Experience of Coding with AI. <https://towardsdatascience.com/the-new-experience-of-coding-with-ai/>.
- Krueger, David** 2026. Ten Different Ways of Thinking about Gradual Disempowerment. [Substack newsletter]. https://therealartificialintelligence.substack.com/p/ten-different-ways-of-thinking-about?utm_campaign=post&triedRedirect=true. <Accessed 15 April 2026>
- Levinson, Stephen C.** 1988. Putting Linguistics on a Proper Footing: Explorations in Goffman’s Concepts of Participation. In P. Drew and A. Wootton (eds). *Erving Goffman. An Interdisciplinary Appreciation*. Oxford: Polity Press. Retrieved from http://pubman.mpg.de/pubman/item/escidoc:66709/component/escidoc:532193/1987_Putting_linguistics_on.pdf
- Lovely, Garrison** forthcoming. *Obsolete: The AI Industry’s Trillion Dollar Race to Replace You and How to Stop It*. OR Books.
- Mao, Shunqi, Wei Guo, Dingxin Zhang, Chaoyi Zhang** and **Weidong Cai** 2026. LLM Nepotism in Organizational Governance. <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2604.09620>.
- Metcalfe, Peter** 2001. *They Lie, We Lie: Getting on with Anthropology*. Routledge.

- Neve, Geert De** 2012. Hidden Reflexivity: Assistants, Informants and the Creation of Anthropological Knowledge. In Geert De Neve and Dr Maya Unnithan-Kumar (eds). *Critical Journeys: The Making Of Anthropologists*. Ashgate Publishing, Ltd.
- Potter, Yujin, Nicholas Crispino, Vincent Siu, Chenguang Wang and Dawn Song** 2026. *Peer-Preservation in Frontier Models*. Retrieved from <https://rdi.berkeley.edu/blog/peer-preservation/>
- Ranganathan, Aruna and Xingqi Maggie Ye** 2026. AI Doesn't Reduce Work—It Intensifies It. <https://hbr.org/2026/02/ai-doesnt-reduce-work-it-intensifies-it>. <Accessed 16 April 2026>
- Ratto, Matt** 2005. 'Don't Fear the Penguins': Negotiating the Trans-local Space of Linux Development. *Current Anthropology* 46 (5): 827–834. <https://doi.org/10.1086/497654>.
- Schimmelpfennig, Robin, Mark Díaz, Vinodkumar Prabhakaran and Aida Davani** 2026. Humanlike AI Design Increases Anthropomorphism but Yields Divergent Outcomes on Engagement and Trust Globally. <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2512.17898>.
- Shi, Hanjing and Dominic DiFranzo** 2026. Human Control Is the Anchor, Not the Answer: Early Divergence of Oversight in Agentic AI Communities. <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2602.09286>.
- Siegel, James T.** 2006. *Naming the Witch*. Stanford University Press.
- Stocking, George W. (ed.)** 1983. *Observers Observed: Essays on Ethnographic Fieldwork*. Madison, Wis: University of Wisconsin Press.
- Taggart, Michael** 2026. I Used AI. It Worked. I Hated It. [Blog]. <https://taggart-tech.com/reckoning/>. <Accessed 16 April 2026>
- Ullman, Ellen** 2013. *Close to the Machine: Technophilia and Its Discontents*. London: Pushkin Press.
- Vaswani, Ashish, Noam Shazeer, Niki Parmar, Jakob Uszkoreit, Llion Jones, Aidan N. Gomez, ... Illia Polosukhin** 2023. Attention Is All You Need. <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.1706.03762>.
- Wilenius, Heikki** in press. Code from Nowhere. *Allegra Laboratory*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.2051111>.